

Final Program

August 25-29, 2025

Hannover, Germany

38TH International Symposium
for the Society of Core Analysts

Nice to know: Our Conference Logo 2025

The organizing team set out to create a logo for the SCA Symposium that not only represents Hannover, but also symbolizes science, progress, innovation – and the spirit of the SCA itself. As you might know, the first successful industrial oil well was established near the town of Wietze, only 25 km from Hannover.

The foundation of the logo is a stylized version of the SCA lettering, complemented on the right by a reinterpreted SCA oil droplet. Sitting atop the lettering is the outline of Hannover's "New Town Hall" – arguably the city's most iconic building, planned and constructed between 1901 and 1913.

At the center of the logo is the likeness of Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646–1716), one of the most renowned universal geniuses of all time. His famous motto "Theoria cum praxi" expresses the idea that theoretical insight should always be paired with practical relevance – and vice versa. This principle also lies at the heart of the SCA: bridging theory and application, from both directions.

The logo is framed with the location and year of the Symposium. Additionally, you will find a variation of this logo on your small giveaway (inside your conference bag) and on the presenters gifts.

Many thanks to **Anne Pogoda-Dorsch (LIAG)** for creating this beautiful conference logo!

From the 2025 President

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

On behalf of the Society and the Board of Directors, it is with great pleasure that I welcome you to the Society of Core Analysts (SCA) International Symposium 2025 in Hannover, Germany.

This year, the symposium workshop will concentrate on the emerging challenges in conventional and special core analysis for CO₂ storage, hydrogen production, and geothermal energy applications. The workshop theme is closely aligned with the current global concern, namely climate change and the emissions from fossil fuel combustion, which are contributing to global warming and extreme weather events. CO₂ storage and the focus on new energy sources are apparent solutions that can help mitigate CO₂ emissions and global warming. This paradigm shift introduces new challenges for core analysis – challenges that I am confident our community is well equipped to address.

The SCA symposium serves as a crucial meeting point for the core analysis community. Its relatively intimate size, devoid of parallel sessions, fosters interactions that connect and build enduring relationships. Moreover, it unites scientists and engineers from both academia and industry. I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks to all those who make this annual event possible. In particular, I am deeply grateful to the VP Technology, Olivier Lopez, and his technical committee for their extensive efforts in the review process and the compilation of the scientific program. My sincere appreciation also goes to the VP Arrangement, Matthias Halisch, for his extraordinary work in organizing the venue and social program. Additionally, I must acknowledge our SCA Executive Director, Melanie Young, who is always ready to assist people. Last, but certainly not least, I want to express my gratitude to all participants who are contributing to this symposium through their papers, presentations, and discussions.

Finally, I wish to convey my profound appreciation to all members of the SCA Board who have dedicated their time and effort to collaborate throughout the year, ensuring the continued success of our Society.

I wish you all an enjoyable and enriching experience in Hannover.

Best regards,

Cyril Caubit
SCA President

From the 2025 VP of Arrangements

Dear Colleagues and Guests!

It is with great enthusiasm that I welcome you to the 2025 SCA Annual Symposium in Hannover, Germany. As we gather for this exciting event, I am honored to host you in one of Europe's most historically rich and culturally vibrant cities. Hannover, a city that masterfully blends tradition with modernity, offers a perfect setting for this year's symposium. Whether you explore the grand Herrenhausen Gardens, marvel at the New Town Hall's unique architecture, or enjoy the city's lively cultural scene, Hannover promises a diverse and memorable experience for all our guests. With its abundant green spaces and bustling urban life, it truly has something to offer for everyone.

Behind the scenes, our team has worked diligently to ensure that each element of this event is thoughtfully planned to offer you an enriching and productive experience. From hands-on technical sessions and in-depth short courses to a variety of networking opportunities, we have designed this symposium to encourage professional growth and foster strong, meaningful connections within our community. Should you have any questions at any time, please do not hesitate to reach out to me!

We are confident that the ideas exchanged and collaborations sparked during this week will have a lasting impact on our field. Your active participation and insight are what make this event a success, and we are excited to share in this journey of learning and discovery with all of you.

A special thank you goes out to our sponsors and vendors, whose generous contributions are instrumental in making this symposium possible. I would also like to express my gratitude to the authors, the technical committee, the volunteers, and to our Executive Director Melanie Young, who have dedicated their time and energy to ensure the success of this conference. Thank you for your support and enthusiasm. I look forward to meeting each of you and making the 2025 symposium a truly exceptional event.

Warmest regards,

Matthias Halisch
2025 VP of Arrangements

From the 2025 VP of Technology

Dear Colleagues and Friends,

Welcome to the 2025 SCA International Symposium in Hannover, Germany!

We, the technical committee and the board, are thrilled to welcome you to the 38th Annual SCA Symposium, which this year will focus on advancing our knowledge of **“Core and Special Core Analysis for Non-Oil and Gas Applications.”**

This year, we received an impressive 89 abstract submissions. Whether or not your abstract was selected, your contributions are deeply valued and play a vital role in the continued success of both the symposium and the SCA community. Following a rigorous review process, we are pleased to announce a technical program comprising **34 oral presentations, 3 alternate orals and 28 posters.**

I extend my heartfelt thanks to the technical committee for their dedication, attention to detail, and unwavering commitment to enhancing the quality of each paper. Thank you as well to all authors and reviewers—your efforts reflect the high standards of technical excellence that define the SCA.

In addition to the technical sessions, this year’s **short course**—titled *“CCA and SCAL for CO₂ and H₂ Storage and Lithium and Geothermal Production”*—will take place on the morning of **August 25th**. Special thanks to **Wael Fadi Al-Asri, Sylvain Thibeau, Souhail Youssef, and Matthias Halisch** for developing what promises to be an insightful and engaging course for our community.

A sincere note of gratitude goes to **Melanie Young**, our SCA Executive Director, whose tireless efforts have been instrumental in shaping this year’s program. I also want to thank **Matthias Halisch**, our VP of Arrangements, for his key role in ensuring the success of this symposium in the beautiful city of **Hannover**.

I look forward to seeing you there and to the inspiring exchange of ideas that will undoubtedly drive our field forward.

Warm regards,

Olivier Lopez
SCA VP of Technology

Current SCA Board

Position	Name	Contact
President	Cyril Caubit	TotalEnergies
Executive Director	Melanie Young	Society of Core Analysts
V P Technology	Olivier Lopez	Equinor
V P Membership	Benjamin Nicot	TotalEnergies
V P Publications	Lesley James	Memorial University
V P Arrangements	Matthias Halisch	LIAG Institute for Applied Geophysics
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Young Professionals Director	Alvaro Muñoz Beltran	Stratum Reservoir
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Director at Large	Matthias Appel	Shell International BV

2025 Technical Committee

The SCA Technical Committee is the backbone of the Society of Core Analysts. Its members rank and evaluate the submitted abstracts and the technical quality of the manuscripts. In the review of each individual manuscript and in-depth discussions with the authors, many hours are spent until a manuscript is accepted. In many cases, the interaction between authors and TC members leads to a higher quality of individual manuscripts. As a result, the annual SCA symposia are packed with high-quality presentations. For this, sincere acknowledgement go to this year's Technical Committee members:

Abdulmajeed Mutairy	Hyung Kwak	Olga Vizika
Abdullah Alajmi	Issa Abu Shiekah	Olivier Lopez
Adam Moss	James Howard	Omid Karoussi
Ali AlSumaiti	Jianchao Cai	Patrick Egermann
Antje van der Net	JinHong Chen	Qinhong Hu
Arjen Cense	John Mills	Reza Askarinezhad
Benjamin Nicot	Jon Burger	Roland Lenormand
Benjamin Anger	Jos Maas	Ryan Armstrong
Carl Fredrik Berg	Josephina Schembre-McCabe	Saman Aryana
Christoph Arns	Jules Reed	Shouxiang Mark Ma
Christopher Jones	Lesley James	Souhail Youssef
Cyril CAUBIT	Matthias Appel	Stacey Althaus
David Potter	Matthias Halisch	Stefano Pruno
Einar Ebeltoft	Matthieu Mascle	Steffen Berg
Fabrice Pairoys	Meshal Algharaib	Subhash Ayirala
Falah Koronfol	Michael Rauschhuber	Thomas Ramstad
Felix Feldmann	Mike Dick	Will Richardson
Franck Nono	Mike Spearing	Xiaolong Yin
Gerald Hamon	Mohamed Ibrahim Al Hammadi	Ying Gao
Guangyuan Sun	Moustafa Dernaika	Yingxue Wang
Hassan Mahani	Muhammad Rehan Hashmet	Vegar Ravlo
Holger Ott	Naif Alqahtani	Rodrigo Surmas

Technical Achievement Darcy Award Recipient

Steffen Berg

- Principal Science Expert, Shell Global Solutions B.V.
- Visiting Reader, Imperial College London since 2015
- PoreLab Scientific Advisory Board since 2022
- Associate Editor, Transp. Por. Med. since 2021
- Associate Editor, SPE Journal since 2019
- SCA Technical Committee since 2013
- Post-Doctoral Researcher, Chemical Engineering at Princeton University from 2003 to 2005
- Ph.D. (Physics) University Mainz, Max Planck Institute for Polymer Research (2002)
- MSc (Materials Science), Universität des Saarlandes, Germany (1998)

Steffen joined Shell's research organization in 2005 and has been working there since – now in the role of Principal Science Expert. His work is focused on developing and applying new concepts of multi-phase transport in porous media and on the utilization of modern imaging technologies to improve the fundamental understanding of structure-transport dependencies for a wide range of porous materials beyond reservoir rocks.

He is an outspoken advocate for embedding academic research in the industrial technology development processes and a very active teacher and mentor in the field of petroleum engineering. In addition to his position of Visiting Reader at Imperial College, Steffen has been teaching courses at graduate university level (Water in Geoprocesses at Utrecht University since 2019; Non-thermal enhanced oil recovery at TU Delft until 2019). He has been the advisor for 5 BSc, 5 MSc, 4 PhD, and 1 PostDoc.

Steffen has, to-date, published more than 120 peer-reviewed articles that have attracted significant interest in the scientific community, leading to more than 10,000 citations and an H-Index of 55. Steffen has won - together with co-authors - the SCA Best Paper Awards in 2009, 11, 13, 14, 16, 18, 19, 21 and 2022. Five of these papers made to the title pages of *Petrophysics*.

The Venue

The Hannover Congress Centrum (HCC) is a premier event location situated in the heart of Hannover, Germany. With a rich history dating back over 100 years, the HCC seamlessly blends tradition with modern functionality. The venue offers more than 44,000 square feet of flexible meeting space, making it one of the largest and most versatile conference centers in the region.

Nestled within the beautiful Stadtpark, the HCC provides a serene and green setting, while being just a short distance from Hannover's vibrant city center. Stunning gardens and scenic paths, offering delegates a peaceful environment to relax between sessions, surround the venue. Nearby, visitors can explore the city's rich cultural heritage, including landmarks such as the Herrenhausen Gardens and the New Town Hall, as well as an array of excellent dining options and shopping districts.

The HCC's state-of-the-art facilities and experienced staff make it the perfect location for international conferences, conventions, and exhibitions, offering both German efficiency and a welcoming atmosphere to create an exceptional experience for all attendees.

Morning Run in Eilenriede Forest – Start Your Conference Day Energized! (Tuesday-Thursday)

Join our morning running group and explore Hannover's beautiful Eilenriede forest! Whether you're a beginner or seasoned runner, choose between our relaxed 5km or challenging 10km routes. Start fresh, network in motion, and enjoy the perfect boost of energy for your conference day! All participants welcome!

- When: starting Tuesday, possibly each morning (exact time to be announced)
- Meeting Point: Main entrance, conference venue
- Routes: Easy 5km or ambitious 10km – suitable for all fitness levels

Women Meet & Greet Breakfast – Connect, Inspire, Empower! Monday, 25th August, 08:00am - 09:30am

Start your Monday morning by joining our special breakfast event for women at all career stages – from academia, industry, and technical fields. Enjoy delicious food, make meaningful connections, and exchange experiences in an informal, inspiring atmosphere. Let's build networks, celebrate diversity, and empower each other before the workshop begins!

- When: Monday morning, starting at 8:00am
- Where: Restaurant of the HCC
- Who: Women from all career stages, backgrounds, and sectors welcome

Kindly sponsored by: Stratum Reservoir

Short Courses – Monday 25th, 8:30am – 12:30pm

Topic: Conventional and Special Core Analysis in CO₂ storage, H₂-/ Li-production, and Geothermal Energy Applications

A special thanks to the presenters who helped put this short workshop together: Wael Fadi Al-Asri, Sylvain Thibeau, Matthias Halisch, and Souhail Youssef

Coffee and tea will be available during breaks. Lunch will be provided to attendees.

Opening Reception – Monday 25th, 5:30pm - 8:30pm

The Opening 'Icebreaker' Reception will take place on the patio adjacent to the vendor exhibition hall. Snacks and drinks will be served to create a relaxed atmosphere, providing a great opportunity to meet and reconnect with both new and long-time colleagues.

Dress Code: Business, Business casual

Kindly Sponsored by: Harbour Energy

Technical Sessions – 25th - 28th August, 8:30am – 4:30pm (Tuesday + Wednesday) / 5:00pm (Monday + Thursday) (With the exception for start at 1:30p.m. on Monday)

Oral presentations: The Symposium will offer 34 oral presentations, each 20 minutes long, followed by 10 minutes for discussion.

Poster sessions: The symposium will offer 31 posters, distributed in three poster sessions. All posters will be on display for the entire Symposium.

Young Professionals Event – Tuesday 26th, 5:30pm - 10:30pm

Join us for a GPS Team Rally through Hannover – a modern urban adventure designed to get you moving, thinking, and teaming up. Armed with puzzles and geo-hints, you and your group will uncover the city's secrets while making new friends along the way. It's all about collaboration, curiosity, and a little bit of friendly competition! Afterwards, we'll wind down the evening at Brauhaus Ernst-August with great food, drinks (alcoholic and non-alcoholic), and even better conversations. The perfect chance to connect, relax, and enjoy Hannover from a different angle.

Dress Code: Casual, good footwear

Awards Gala Dinner – Wednesday 27th, 6:30pm - 10:30pm

The Gala Dinner will be held at the stunning Maharajah's Palace within Hannover Zoo, offering a unique and exotic setting for this special evening. The event will begin with a reception, where guests can enjoy drinks and mingle in a vibrant atmosphere. Dinner will feature a delightful blend of modern and traditional German cuisine, providing a culinary experience that reflects both innovation and heritage. As night falls, a spectacular fire show will light up the evening, creating a memorable finale to this extraordinary event.

Dress code: Business / Business Casual

Gala Dinner is kindly sponsored by: Math2Market, Chevron and Shell

Optional Field Trip – Friday 29th, 8:30am - 7:00pm

Join us for an exciting day trip to the UNESCO World Heritage site of Goslar, rich in history and culture. We will depart from the Hannover Congress Centrum at 8:30 a.m. on Friday 29th, and head to the famous Rammelsberg, where a guided tour will introduce you to both the historical and modern aspects of mining in the region.

After the tour, we will enjoy a traditional "Oberharzer Brotzeit" lunch, featuring local specialties at Rammelsberg. Following lunch, we will explore Goslar's charming historic old town, with a 90-minute guided tour that delves into the city's centuries-old history. After the tour, participants will have free time to explore the sights, including the Imperial Palace and the beautiful medieval streets, or simply relax in one of the many cafes with coffee, ice cream and cake.

- Transportation and lunch provided
- Departure from Hannover Congress Centrum: 8:30 am
- Rammelsberg Tour: until lunch
- Lunch: Traditional "Oberharzer Brotzeit" at Rammelsberg Casino
- Goslar guided Old Town Tour: 1:30 pm to 3 pm
- Free time: Explore Goslar at your leisure 3pm to 5pm
- Return to Hannover Congress Centrum: 6:30 pm to 7 pm

Dress code: Appropriate Casual. As it might get little wet / slippery in the old mining facility, proper hiking shoes and a robust sweater/jacket are recommended.

Publication of Proceedings

The proceedings are prepared in online format at the SCA website (<https://www.scaweb.org>) and login details will be given at the Symposium to all registered participants.

After the Symposium, all manuscripts will be published without charge at SCA's new online community repository on the Zenodo website (including keyword search opportunities and DOI numbers).

SCA Zenodo Repository

The SCA has decided to no longer carry printed copies of the proceedings.

Exhibitors

Monday: 8:30am – 5:00pm	*Exhibition Build-up starts at 8:30am
Tuesday: 8:30am – 4:30pm	
Wednesday: 8:30am – 4:30pm	
Thursday: 8:30am – 5:00pm	*Exhibition Break-down can start after the afternoon break and complete by 5pm

AMETEK Chandler Engineering - AMETEK Chandler Engineering is a global leader of HPHT instrumentation for the Oil and Gas industry. Chandler Engineering has the expertise in the design and implementation of Core Flow Systems for Reservoir Analysis, Carbon Utilization and Storage (CUS), Corrosion and Scale Testing, including Custom Engineered SCAL Solutions and our line of Quizix precision pump products. We look forward to working with you to meet today's challenges!

Baker Hughes Digital Solutions GmbH - We are one of the world's leading manufacturers of X-ray inspection systems and industrial computed tomography systems for non-destructive failure analysis and 3D metrology. The CSC in Wunstorf offers customers the world's largest range of professional X-ray services using phoenix|x-ray systems. These services include X-ray inspection, industrial computed tomography (CT), training, and technical expertise.

Beijing Limecho Technology Co. Ltd - Beijing Limecho Technology Co., Ltd is a high-tech company focusing on producing high-end MR (Magnetic Resonance) equipment and providing high-quality MR technical services. The company is committed to different applications of MR, providing complete and effective technical solutions for domestic and foreign customers from the areas of energy , materials, chemical industry, bio-medicine, food, archaeology, and others. Limecho is a National high-tech enterprise, a Beijing high-level returned overseas scholar enterprise, a member of Consortium for Magnetic Resonance Application Technology in the oil & gas industry, a Beijing New Fourth Board enterprise, and a member of China Instrument and Control Society.

Core Laboratories - Core Laboratories is a leading provider of proprietary and patented reservoir description and production enhancement services and products. These services and products enable the company's clients to optimize reservoir performance and maximize hydrocarbon recovery from their producing fields. The company has over 70 offices in more than 50 countries and is located in every major oil-producing province in the world.

CYDAREX - CYDAREX is a specialized French company providing advanced solutions for core and cuttings analysis. Originally, a spin-off of the French Institute of Petroleum (IFPEN), CYDAREX has been fully independent for 20 years. CYDAREX supports companies in the domains of petroleum, hydrogen storage, and CO₂ sequestration, through consulting, training, laboratory equipment, and software. Its software, CYDAR™, is a powerful platform for the design and the interpretation of core analysis experiments, including CCA, SCAL, and advanced EOR protocols. CYDAR enables efficient analyses for MICP, porous plate, relative permeability, centrifugation, and history matching, on both homogeneous and heterogeneous samples. It now includes a module for two-phase flow experiments with polymer, low-salinity, and surfactant flooding.

More than 80 oil companies, research institutions, and service providers in over 20 countries trust CYDAR. CYDAR offers a validated, user-friendly solution that increases efficiency, reduces interpretation time, improves traceability, and supports long-term skill development across teams.

DCI Corporation - DCI offers innovative solutions to your core testing requirements. From turnkey systems to system components, we can help you with your laboratory needs. DCI designs and manufactures both custom and standard core holders, accumulators, syringe pumps, acoustic separators, core flood systems, electrical resistivity systems, rock mechanics systems and much more. Stop by our booth to see how DCI can help you make better measurements on core properties.

fluidXlab GmbH - fluidXlab GmbH develops advanced microfluidic systems to study multiphase flow in porous media under reservoir-relevant pressure and temperature conditions. Our HPHT platform InspIOR® enables fast, visual screening of PVT, EOR/IOR, and gas storage processes — using real reservoir fluids and chips that resemble rock structures. We support energy companies and research institutions in accelerating screening, optimizing injection strategies, and reducing experimental overhead. (www.fluidxlab.com)

Gesteinslabor Jahns - Gesteinslabor Dr Eberhard Jahns was established in 1997 as an independent provider of rock testing services. We carry out physical, mechanical and poroelastic laboratory experiments on rock to determine relevant data for safety and productivity modelling. In addition to standard tests, we specialise in providing high-precision solutions for specific customer requirements, offering sophisticated, bespoke testing procedures. We support customers in the oil and gas, deep geothermal energy, CCS, nuclear waste disposal and underground gas storage industries. Our laboratory is heavily involved in researching the integrity of hydrogen storage facilities, for example by determining the threshold pressure of caprock against hydrogen, methane and their mixtures. We also contribute significantly to the SCAN project, which investigates the Dutch subsurface for potential geothermal heat production.

Green Imaging Technologies, Inc - Green Imaging is the industry leader in NMR rock core analysis. Our software is the backbone of the Oxford GeoSpec line of NMR Rock Core Analyzers, which are used by all major oil producers, oil service companies and the most active research institutes worldwide. Our customers have access to exclusive, patented measurements including NMR capillary pressure and quantitative saturation profiles. Our team of experts is focused on rock core analysis, and as such have developed relationships with the most respected researchers and experts in the NMR rock core analysis field. Providing solutions for reservoir characterization, well log calibration, carbon storage and many other applications, we are always looking for new ways to apply NMR to new challenges. We look forward to talking to current and potential NMR users about how NMR can help them solve their reservoir puzzles.

Math2Market GmbH - Math2Market develops GeoDict, a comprehensive simulation software solution that includes software, support, project work, user training, and custom developments and extensions. The GeoDict package specifically designed for Digital Rock Physics and Digital Core Analysis (DRP-DCA) combines with imaging capabilities, to perform these workflows accurately, completely, digitally, and in-house. It boasts exceptionally fast runtimes, the ability to handle extremely large datasets, and low hardware requirements or cloud usage. Recently added features include the simulation of two-phase flow with the entire hysteresis cycle and the digital analysis of rocks for CO₂ sequestration techniques and storage mechanisms.

Oxford Instruments - Oxford Instruments is a leader in scientific instrumentation, with a long history of utilizing expertise and global reach to bring tools to market to aid advanced scientific studies. At SCA, Oxford Instruments will be collaborating with Green Imaging to display the GeoSpec NMR Rock Core Analyzer product line. The GeoSpec line has been the market leader for many years and continues to expand the petrophysical parameters that can be measured with NMR rock core analyzers. We look forward to discussing your rock core analysis requirements.

PanTerra Geoconsultants BV - PanTerra Geoconsultants is an experienced, professional laboratory service provider for core analysis, reservoir fluid characterisation, geology and subsurface evaluations to the global energy industry. PanTerra is based in The Netherlands and in Oman. With decades of experience, our teams work on projects for oil & gas companies, CCUS and geothermal.

Petricore - Petricore delivers a comprehensive suite of Rock Laboratory Services, including Routine Core Analysis, Special Core Analysis (SCAL), Digital Rock Analysis, and Wellsite Services. With specialized teams based in Mexico, the USA, and Norway, we are committed to quality, precision, and personalized customer care. Our experts work closely with clients to provide tailored solutions that meet their specific technical and operational needs—always ready to support and add value at every stage.

Qmineral - Qmineral is your preferred mineralogy lab. Having won the Reynolds cup - aka the world championship of mineralogy - twice, it is one of the leading labs in the world when it comes to (clay) mineral analyses. Beside classical lab services, Qmineral has developed a software, named HSMQ - High Speed Mineralogical Quantification, for the nearly instant quantification of minerals in rocks and powders from a FTIR measurement. HSMQ is developed for on-site application as for gathering massive amounts of data in core repositories, for the analysis of cuttings on drill rigs or for quality control in industrial/mining environments.

RS-Systems AS - RS Systems is an independent Norwegian based company, which develops, designs and manufactures laboratory set-ups for advanced laboratory analysis of rock and fluid properties.

Stratum Reservoir - Stratum Reservoir is a global team of applied geoscience specialists. With decades of experience and a comprehensive range of services, we empower our clients to discover and develop sustainable energy resources. We support divestiture strategies and energy resource investments by analyzing and interpreting rocks and fluids in our laboratories worldwide. Our expertise in reservoir characterization delivers deep scientific insights that drive innovation and informed decision-making across the subsurface industry.

Thermo Fisher Scientific – We are the world leader in serving science. Our mission is to enable our customers to make the world healthier, cleaner and safer. Our innovative solutions for electron microscopy, surface analysis, and microanalysis help materials science researchers advance their sample characterization to gain deeper insight into the physical and chemical properties of materials from the macroscale to the nanoscale. Our multiscale, multimodal solutions cover a broad range of applications across dozens of industries and research fields, serving customers in academia, government, and industry. Our TEMs, DualBeam™ FIB-SEMs, comprehensive portfolio of SEMs, XPS, and microanalysis solutions, combined with software suites, take customers from questions to usable data by combining high-resolution imaging with physical, chemical, elemental, mechanical, and electrical analysis across scales and modes.

Vinci Technologies/Floxlab - Vinci Technologies is an engineering company specialized in the design and manufacture of high-pressure/high-temperature laboratory instruments for rock and fluid analysis, as well as high-pressure metering pumps. Our product line includes equipment for relative permeability and capillary pressure measurements, PVT studies, and triaxial rock compression testing. These versatile systems enable new market opportunities and help address key challenges in carbon sequestration, hydrogen storage and geothermal energy.

Vindum Engineering Inc. - MANUFACTURER OF PRECISION HIGH PRESSURE PULSE-FREE PUMPS and VALVES

VIPR Pumps: Large Volume Cylinder Pumps

- Easily upgrade to Continuous Pulse-Free Flow with 2 pumps
- Syringe Piston Design with Cylinder Wash Area
- Includes CV (Constant Volume) Valves Standard
- Includes VPware software for full control and monitoring
- Compatible with gases or liquids, including CO₂

VP Pumps: High Precision, Continuous Pulse-Free Metering Pumps

- Next generation design: lower cost, higher performance
- Models up to 25,000 psi
- Options for ambient or high-temperature operation (up to 160°C)
- Compatible with gases or liquids, including CO₂

CV Valves: Constant-Volume, High-Pressure Valves

- Air activation for reliable switching
- Handles high temperature (up to 300°C)
- Available in 2-Way and 3-Way configurations

MV Hastelloy Valves & Fittings: Modular Manual Valve System

- Mountable, compact design saves valuable system space
- Uses replaceable O-ring seals (multiple material options)
- Cost effective Hastelloy construction
- In-stock and ready for immediate delivery

Hastelloy C-276 Tubing: In stock for immediate delivery

Floor Plan

Short Course Program
 Conventional and Special Core Analysis in CO₂ storage, H₂ & Li production,
 and Geothermal Energy Applications

August 25, 2025

SCA Short Course	
Moderator: Olivier Lopez / Matthias Halisch	
8:30 - 8:40	Welcome and safety moment (Matthias Halisch)
8:40 - 8:50	SCA Short Course Introduction Presenter: Olivier Lopez
8:50 - 9:40	Implications of CCA and SCAL for CO ₂ Storage Presenter: Wael Fadi Al-Asri (Geological Survey of Denmark)
9:40 - 10:30	The two main impacts that may limit CO ₂ storage resources in a saline aquifer Presenter: Sylvain Thibeau (TotalEnergies)
10:30 - 10:50	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
Moderator: Olivier Lopez / Matthias Halisch	
10:50 - 11:40	CAL and SCAL for Geothermal Field Development Presenter: Matthias Halisch (LIAG)
11:40 - 12:30	CAL and SCAL for H ₂ Storage and Production Presenter: Souhail Youssef (IFPEN)
12:30 - 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: TotalEnergies

Technical Program	
Monday, August 25, 2024	
7:30 - 5:00	Registration Desk Open
1:30 - 3:00	Session 1: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation I Chairs: A. Almutairi & M. Dick
SCA1052	In-Situ Two- and Three-Phase Saturation Monitoring Using Dual-Resonance $^1\text{H}/^{23}\text{Na}$ MRI During Coreflooding de Kort et al.
SCA1012	Imaging-based Dispersion in CT-Coreflooding Experiments Fadili & Berg
SCA1037	Defining absolute permeability for CO_2 injection projects: scope for increased economic storage capacity Maas et al.
3:00 - 3:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
3:30 - 5:00	Session 2: Pore-Scale Imaging and Modelling I Chairs: S. Youssef & R. Armstrong
SCA1028	Using Minkowski Functionals to Improve the Accuracy of Residual Gas Saturation (N_2 , CH_4 , H_2) from μ -CT Core Flooding Experiments Gao et al.
SCA1013	Digital SCAL in Complex Carbonates by the Density Functional Hydrodynamics Method Klemin et al.
SCA1081	Multi-scale Experimental Study of Trapped Gas Mobilization in Carbonate Rocks Joshi et al.
5:30 - 8:30	Opening Reception "Icebreaker Reception" Kindly Sponsored by: Harbour Energy

Tuesday, August 26, 2025	
8:00 - 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 9:30	Session 3: Laboratory Core Analysis I Chairs: J. Maas & J. Reeds
SCA1100	Characterization of Uncertainty Sources of Special Core Analysis Compan et al.
SCA1059	Laboratory validation of geoelectrical models for permeability prediction Weller et al.
9:30 - 10:00	Exhibitor Presentations
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
10:30 - 12:00	Session 4: Subsurface Storage Chairs: M. Masde & S. Pruno
SCA1044	Leveraging Analogues for CO ₂ Core Flood Experiments: Enhancing Reservoir Simulation Inputs Petersen et al.
SCA1038	Geochemical Reactions in Reservoir Rock and Capillary Sealing Capacity of Caprock in the Underground Gas Storage Complex Rehden Langanke et al.
SCA1089	Equilibrium Modelling of CO ₂ -Brine Systems for Geological Carbon Storage Applications: Experimental Measurements and Thermodynamic Modelling Alimohammadi et al.
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: Stratum Reservoir
1:00 - 1:30	Exhibitor presentations
1:30 - 2:00	Poster Presentations I (check your session number in poster list)

2:00 - 3:00	Coffee Break and Poster Session I (PS I) Kindly Sponsored by: Waygate Technologies
3:00 - 4:30	Session 5: Wettability Chairs: O. Karoussi & F. Pairoys
SCA1097	Flow-dependency aspects in SCAL of steady-state two-phase flow in model pore networks Mouravas et al.
SCA1074	Towards faster Amott index measurement: Amott Express Technique Rochereau et al.
SCA1075	Impact of Dopants on SCAL Experiments, Phase II Danielczick et al.
5:30 - 10:30	Young Professional Event Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
Wednesday, August 27, 2025	
8:15 - 5:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 10:00	Session 6: Improved SCAL Techniques and Interpretation II Chairs: J. Reeds & M. Demaiika
SCA1020	On-site FTIR analysis for accurate mineralogical Screening of cuttings and core: a case study of the Boom Clay Adriaens et al.
SCA1027	SCAL Workflow for Heterogeneous Pre-salt Carbonate Rocks Gao et al.
SCA1011	Presence of Heterogeneities in Rocks during Laboratory Waterfloods: A Case Study Highlighting Differences in Relative Permeabilities between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous 1D Approaches Pairoys et al.
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: XXX

10:30 - 12:00	Session 7: Displacement Mechanisms EOR / IOR and Reactive Transport I Chairs: C. Caubit & S. Youssef
SCA1070	Hysteresis in Relative Permeability from Cyclic Water-Oil Corefloods Fernandes et al.
SCA1080	Role of limestone micro-porosity on dissolution patterns during reactive transport with carbonated water Masde et al.
SCA1039	Gas-Oil interaction and Gravity impact on high permeability WAG experiments Puyou et al.
12:00 - 1:00	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
1:00 - 2:00	Session 8: Displacement Mechanisms EOR / IOR and Reactive Transport II Chairs: L. James & V. Ravlo
SCA1030	Deep Learning Assisted Processing of Synchrotron-based Micro-CT Imaging of Fast, Dynamic Multiphase Flow in Porous Media Mathew et al.
SCA1083	The Role of Interfacial Tension in Nanobubble-Enhanced Oil Recovery Taman et al.
2:00 - 2:30	Poster Presentations II (check your session number in poster list)
2:30 - 3:30	Coffee Break and Poster Session II (PS II) Kindly Sponsored by: Waygate Technologies
3:30 - 4:30	Session 9: Unconventional and Shales Chairs: J. Reeds & D. Potter
SCA1035	The effects of confinement and wettability on the phase behavior of pure and multicomponent fluids in nanoporous media Nguyen & Piri
SCA1058	Experimental Investigation of Fracture–Matrix Flow Using CT Imaging Panaitescu et al.

6:30 - 10:30	Gala Dinner Kindly Sponsored by: Math2Market GmbH, Chevron and Shell
Thursday, August 28, 2025	
8:30 - 3:00	Registration Desk Open
8:30 - 10:00	Session 10: Pore-Scale Imaging and Modelling II Chairs: N. Alqahtani & E. Ebeltoft
SCA1015	A Novel Grain-Contact Modeling Approach for Enhanced Petro-Elastic Simulations in Digital Rock Halisch et al.
SCA1079	HSR-NMR Scanner for High-Throughput Measurement of Fluids Distribution in Whole Cores Chen et al.
SCA1055	Investigating dispersive H ₂ and CO ₂ transport by means of medical-CT and GC-Supported core flooding experiments Stiedl et al.
10:00 - 10:30	Coffee Break Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
10:30 - 12:00	Session 11: NMR & MRI Chairs: M. Appel & C. Arns
SCA1068	Practical Limitations of Low Field NMR Measurements of ¹³ C and ²³ Na Dick et al.
SCA1069	Monitoring Salt Precipitation in Porous Media Using ²³ Na MRI: Implications for CO ₂ Storage Ansaribaranghar et al.
SCA1024	A Rock Catalog Data Study for Extending NMR Fluid Substitution to Sandstone Thern et al.
12:00 - 12:30	Business Meeting

12:30 - 1:30	Lunch Kindly Sponsored by: XXX
1:30 - 2:00	Poster Presentations III (check your session number in poster list)
2:00 - 3:00	Coffee Break and Poster Session III (PS III) Kindly Sponsored by: Waygate Technologies
3:00 - 5:00	Session 12: Laboratory Core Analysis II Chairs: M. Halisch & L. James
SCA1071	Improved Method of Relative Permeability Measurements Using Steady State Technique Alratrout & Shehata
SCA1017	The responses of electrical resistivity tools to CO ₂ dissolution in brine and carbon mineralization – Implication for Monitoring Underground CO ₂ Sequestration Abdulrauf
SCA1040	Using the fluctuation-dissipation theorem to measure total phase mobility during fractional flow experiments Alfazazi et al.
SCA1031	Utilisation of Extended Slow Heating (ESH) pyrolysis and core analysis for determination of oil saturations and porosity correction Al-Masri et al.
5:00	Closing Remarks

Alternate Orals

Alternation Orals	
SCA1062 (PS I)	Measurements of Electrical Resistivity Index of Tight Gas Sandstones Using Vapor Desorption Method, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, and Corrections for effect of clay conductivity, salinity and density change Badhafere et al.
SCA1050 (PS I)	Sensitivity analysis for capillary pressure data from centrifuge considering different rotation speed range, centrifuge models, and sample size Winter et al.
SCA1034 (PS I)	Characterization of sandstone and carbonate rocks using dual-energy X-ray computed tomography for sample selection in coreflooding tests Vargas et al.

Posters Presentations

Posters with Manuscript	
SCA1014 (PS I)	Efficient True Resistivity Prediction and Time Optimization in PcRI Measurements: A Results-Driven Approach Nourani et al.
SCA1022 (PS I)	Pore-scale clogging simulations for a Geothermal Reservoir under lithostatic pressure and realistic tail water injection scenarios Njeru et al.
SCA1042 (PS I)	Monitoring of Wettability Behaviour During Capillary Pressure Measurements at Reservoir Conditions: An Alternative Experimental Approach Nourani et al.
SCA1060 (PS I)	A Comparison of Lithology Predictors in Some Thin Bedded Gas Turbidite Reservoirs using Conventional and Quantum Neural Networks Potter & Le
SCA1061 (PS I)	Investigating NMR T ₂ -Cutoffs: Towards Better Reservoir Characterization Ali et al.
SCA1067 (PS I)	Effective Symbolic Regression-Based Petrophysical Model Development Workflow and Efficient Software Tool for Enabling Easy Utilization Shao & Chen

SCA1054 (PS I)	Experimental investigation on wettability alteration of Glauconitic sandstone during CO ₂ Storage Al-Masri et al.
SCA1088 (PS II)	Impact of Representative Elemental Volume on Steady-State and Unsteady-State Relative Permeability Sun et al.
SCA1048 (PS II)	Evaluation of relative permeability using the multi-flow method in carbonate rocks with highly heterogeneity considering the preservation of wettability through a mild cleaning process Ruidiaz et al.
SCA1049 (PS II)	Evaluation of the dynamic's adsorption of polar components during the wettability restoration of carbonate rocks from Brazilian pre-salt reservoirs and their preservation for relative permeability tests Ruidiaz et al.
Posters without Manuscript	
SCA1016 (PS II)	3D core microstructure generation and reconstruction method based on two-stage diffusion modeling Wang et al.
SCA1025 (PS II)	An Advanced Micro-CT System for Core Analysis: Comparison, Challenges and Potential in the Sub-Micrometer Range Halisch et al.
SCA1036 (PS II)	Evaluation of Core Microstructure by Using High-Pressure MICP Aboujafar et al.
SCA1041 (PS II)	Revision of the clay coring technique based on an analysis of drilling-induced artefacts Van Baelen et al.
SCA1046 (PS II)	Unravelling the lithological control on the thermal properties of deep clay formations Van Baelen et al.
SCA1056 (PS II)	A Novel Porous Plate Method for Hydrogen Capillary Pressure Hysteresis with In-Situ Micro-CT Imaging Adila et al.

SCA1063 (PS II)	The responses of electrical resistivity tools to CO ₂ dissolution in brine and carbon mineralization – Implication for Monitoring Underground CO ₂ Sequestration Adebayo et al.
SCA1065 (PS III)	Uncertainty Study of Continuous, Sparse and Discrete NMR Inversions Gao et al.
SCA1073 (PS III)	Sensitivity of NMR T ₂ Relaxation Responses in Chalk to High-Susceptibility Inclusions Ams et al.
SCA1078 (PS III)	Enhanced Permeability Field Estimation in Carbonate Rocks Using Tracer Tests and X-Ray Computed Tomography Oliveira et al.
SCA1082 (PS III)	CO ₂ Trapping Curves from Digital Rock Physics: Application to Austrian Rock Types Brandstaetter et al.
SCA1086 (PS III)	A Data-Driven Approach to Synthetic Relative Permeability Prediction and Dynamic Rock Typing Using Unsupervised Machine Learning Ainesazi et al.
SCA1091 (PS III)	Best Practice Approach to Measure Dead Volume in Core Flooding Oven Systems James et al.
SCA1093 (PS III)	Best Practice Approach to Measure Viscosity of Supercritical CO ₂ and Live CO ₂ -Brine Mixtures at High Temperature and Pressure Conditions James et al.
SCA1098 (PS III)	The influence of deformation bands on petrophysical parameters in connection with CT images and well logs Puskar et al.
SCA1099 (PS III)	New aspects in the interpretation of CT images in carbonate rocks Puskar et al.
SCA1084 (PS III)	Physicochemical interactions between Carbonates/Brine/CO ₂ and their impact on Residual Trapping: Application for CO ₂ geo-storage Mouallem et al.
SCA1053 (PS III)	Augmenting Pore Scale Experimentation and Modeling workflows to hydrogen storage Rucker et al.

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